

To the Functional Evidence Community,

Thank you to everyone that attended the February Functional Evidence Discussion Forum. We had excellent participation and interesting discussion, and we appreciate you supporting our growing field. Thank you especially to Andy Ng and Elizabeth Farnsworth for sharing assays for discussion.

We would like to share a summary of the session with you, including the content and results of the polls. As part of the continuing forum, we will endeavour to share this information with the forum members after each session. We hope you find this useful, please let us know if you have any suggestions.

Thank you again for being part of the community and see you at the next session.

Kind Regards,

Rehan Villani and The AusMAVE Education Team

Announcements

[Join the Clinical Genomics Laboratory Community](#)

Hosted by GA4GH and ClinGen, the [Clinical Genomics Laboratory Community \(CGLC\)](#) aims to connect clinical labs around the globe, with the aim of fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and standards development.

[Join the community](#)

[48th Human Genetics Society of Australasia Annual Scientific Meeting](#)

The HGSA Annual Scientific Meeting will be held Friday 15th to Monday 18th August 2025 at the International Convention Centre (ICC) Sydney. Go to the [HGSA 48th Annual Scientific Meeting webpage](#) for more information.

Registrations now open. Abstracts close 17th April 2025.

[The Functional Evidence Discussion Forum](#)

The next session will be held on the 14th of May 2025, 1:00pm AEST. If you have not already registered for the mailing list, please [register for the forum](#) to be added to the mailing list and to receive calendar invitations for the upcoming forum sessions.

Forum Information

Terms of Reference

We provide a draft version of the Terms of Reference, *deadline for comments extended until 30 May 2025*, after which the document will be finalised and made public for participants of the Functional Evidence Discussion Community.

[Terms of Reference](#) (draft)

Online Platform

At the session we polled the audience in regards to an online, chat based system for discussion functional evidence. 29/47 supported an online, web-page based chat group (e.g. of Wix group given) and 27/47 supported a Slack or Zulip App based chat group.

We will initiate an online chat platform before the next session. Look for our announcements regarding this in the next forum session.

The Session: Patch Clamp Assays

The Functional Evidence Discussion Forum held on 27th February 2025 focussed on Patch clamp assays, which are used to assess the current across a membrane, or membrane potential of a cell (Ma et al., 2024). High-throughput patch clamp assays for KCNH2 (Thomson et al., 2024) and SCN5A were presented by Dr Chai-Ann Ng, and a smaller patch clamp assay investigating 6 epilepsy related variants in SCN1A was discussed by Elizabeth Farnsworth (Bechi et al., 2015).

Presenter 1 Summary

Dr Chai-Ann Ng, Senior Staff Scientist, Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute

Dr Ng presented an automated Patch clamp assay for KCNH2 and SCN5A variants for long QT Syndrome type 2 and Brugada Syndrome (O'Neill et al., 2024). He showed that the assays can be calibrated using a large number of controls (clinical reference set controls)(Ng et al., 2025) to generate validated evidence suitable for use at the PS3 strong level. A number of clinical testing laboratories (Invitae, NHS labs, VCGS, NSW Health Pathology, GHQ) are currently engaged to perform functional assessments of their VUS using the assay. Dr Ng hopes to establish research functional testing for all channelopathies and has been championing closer cooperation and collaboration between clinical and research teams.

[Slides - Integration of functional evidence to support the pathogenicity of ion channel variants](#) by Chai-Ann Ng

Poll results

The Functional Evidence Discussion Forum participants were asked about their use and opinion of the specific assays presented by Dr Ng. While only a few had used the assay results presented in classification, the majority agreed that they would (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Use of the presented Patch Clamp assays in current practice. A) 21/24 poll participants have used the patch clamp assays presented in the session for evidence in classification. B) 14/24 poll participants indicated that they would use the patch clamp assays for variant classification.

In regards to the assays presented in the session, most participants would be comfortable applying supporting or moderate pathogenic evidence, but were less comfortable applying other levels of evidence, pathogenic strong or benign (Figure 2). Participants also indicated that many (16/24) would likely apply the evidence as presented, though 10/24 would investigate further first before doing this.

Figure 2. Participants showed that they would be comfortable applying the majority of evidence categories for the patch clamp assays, though were most comfortable applying Pathogenic supporting level.

We also asked regarding patch clamp assays in general. Generally speaking there was a good level of support for the clinical use of these assays, and most were happy with the assay as a valid type of evidence. While not many had used/calibrated the assays, the approach presented by Dr Ng was generally well supported by the audience.

Presenter 2 Summary

Elizabeth Farnsworth, Senior Scientific Officer, The Children's Hospital, Westmead NSW.

Elizabeth presented a variant in SCN1A, NM_001165963.4 (SCN1A):c.[4096G>A];[=] p.[(Val1366Ile)];[=], that was identified in an affected child with an unaffected mother. The variant has been previously identified in atypical Dravet (Takayama et al., 2014) and variants in this gene are associated with GEFS+ and a range of associated epilepsy syndromes. A summary of the variant was presented, see slides for more information.

The session discussed a patch clamp assay (Bechi et al., 2015) assessing impact of variants on Na⁺ channel Nav1.1 (SCN1A). The assay was a patch clamp assay in tsA-201 cells, (human embryonic kidney), the variants introduced via tagged cDNA. 6 variants were analysed, compared to wildtype construct, with varied/conflicting ClinVar classifications. This means the assay did not meet current ClinGen recommendation for OddsPath calculation (Brnich et al., 2019).

[Slides - Discussing the use of Bechi et al. 2015 for SCN1A variant](#) by Elizabeth Farnsworth

Participant poll results

The majority of participants (14/25) believed that the patch clamp assay presented would not be applicable as evidence in classification of the SCN1A Val1366Ile variant, a smaller proportion indicated supporting level pathogenic evidence may apply (PS3_supporting). There was however variation in opinion, and clearly lower confidence in this assay compared to the previous higher throughput assays presented. The participants raised the difficulty in evaluating evidence strength with the low number of variants investigated in the assay. The lack of controls used in the assay was identified as a particular barrier, and in fact 23/25 participants agreed that absence of controls was a barrier when considering this assay type/class (in general) for use as evidence in variant classification.

Figure 3. Evidence level that participants would apply in classification of SCN1A variation based on the assay by Bechi et al. 2015. Based on the Patch clamp assay presented in Bechi et al. 2015 PMID: 25576396, participants were asked to indicate which evidence level would apply for the variant NM_001165963.4 (SCN1A):c.[4096G>A];[=] p.[(Val1366Ile)];[=]

Session Summary

The Discussion Forum presentations may impact how forum participants evaluate/use assays in classification.

Forum participants indicated that they had increased comfort in evaluating these (patch clamp) assays after the presentations, and suggested this may increase the chance that they apply the assays as evidence (where appropriately evaluated).

Figure 4. Impact of presentations on assay use. Participants were asked to indicate according to the provided categories (X-axis), “How did the presentations impact how you might evaluate/use these assays in classification?”

Take home messages

Confidence in the evidence applicable from functional assay data is dependent on the number (and type) of controls variants included in an assay. Many have had the problem of not enough controls (particularly benign/pathogenic clinical reference set controls) in published assays, especially with Patch clamp assays. Considering this, it was universally agreed that Dr Ng’s assays had particular strength in the number of clinical and benign controls.

- The Discussion Forum Participants indicated that they did not always fully understand functional assay procedures or have time to do so, which impacted their confidence in applying functional evidence.
- The forum asked for support calculating OddsPath, to help translating functional assays.
- Though polls suggest that independent expert review would facilitate evidence use, advice was given in the session to ‘Don’t blindly follow rules, apply clinical judgement’ – Ben Lundie.

References

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